

Teachers' and Students' Causal Explanations for Classroom Misbehavior: Similarities and Differences

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Abstract : This study aimed to examine the similarities and differences between teachers' and students' causal explanations of classroom misbehavior. In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with twelve teachers and eighteen Grade 7-9 students. The qualitative data were analyzed, in which the attributed causes of classroom misbehavior were categorized into student, family, school, and peer factors. Findings showed that both interviewed teachers and students shared similarity in attributing to student factors, such as 'fun and pleasure seeking' and 'attention seeking' as the leading causes of misbehavior. However, the students accounted to school factors, particularly 'boring lessons' as the next attributed causes, while the teachers accounted to family factors, such as 'lack of parent demandingness'. By delineating the factors at student, family, school, and peer levels, these findings help drawing corresponding implications for preventing and mitigating misbehavior in school.

Keywords : causal explanation, misbehavior, student, teacher

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